

UNPATH'D WATERS: Searching and Linking

Research Report: Work Package 2

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Searching and linking: Work Package 2

1.1 Introduction

Archaeological data, and in particular that relating to maritime archaeology, is diverse and complex. It has accrued over more than a century of research, been stored in a variety of formats and structures, and divided between different national agencies, community groups, museums and non-governmental organisations. It relates to surviving tangible physical objects, features and settings as well as things which no longer exist and intangible heritage in the form of knowledge, skills, sense of place and oral history. These traits are not unique to archaeological, or maritime archaeological heritage, but their diversity and complexity is strongly expressed through the datasets we compiled and had to work with on Unpath'd Waters.

This complexity speak directly to the challenge recognised by *Towards a National Collection* and its five overarching objectives. These were:

- to begin to dissolve barriers between different collections
- to open up collections to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research
- to extend researcher and public access beyond the physical boundaries of their location
- to benefit a diverse range of audiences
- to be active and of benefit across the UK
- to provide clear evidence and exemplars that support enhanced funding going forward

Unpath'd Waters addressed each of these objectives. In so doing it also acknowledged our prior understanding of the history and current status of major national data sources, collections and archives. At its heart there was a desire to engage with this opportunity to explore what a national collection for maritime heritage might look like and how it could be delivered. It was recognised from the start that this would require engagement with a variety of data types, sources, stakeholders, and perspectives. Critically the variability in data would need to be addressed, to help make it Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable ([FAIR](#)). While in past decades such work would heavily rely on domain specialists harmonising records by hand, an opportunity existed to explore how recent developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI) might help with this process. This was the work of Work Package 2, led by the University of Southampton, with support from a wide range of consortium organisations, and in particular the Archaeological Data Service (Work Package 1), each of the national heritage agencies.

This document should be read in conjunction with the overarching Unpath'd Waters final report, which provides both detail and connective narrative. This report offers additional text and detail on work package two activities.

1.2 Aims & Objectives

The aim of work package two was to explore ‘How can we transform our ability to search’ the collections aggregated in [work package one](#), the process of which is set out in Richards et al. (2025). In particular it looked to harness recent developments in artificial Intelligence and machine learning and build on work done in the *Towards a National Collection* [Heritage Connector Foundation Project](#) (Winters et al. 2022), to enrich sparse data, increase interoperability and enable data search and discoverability. Within the project proposal we identified the following objectives:

- To trial low-shot and zero-shot approaches to enriching sparse data
- To use the above techniques to unlock additional spatial and temporal data potential
- To explore potential for application of computer vision techniques.

Work package two was closely linked to work package one, in that it was understood that some data gathered during the aggregation process was likely to require enrichment to enable mapping to the chosen ontology and data structure. Further, given the sparse and variable nature of some metadata, this process of enhancement would speak directly to the core challenges of *Towards a National Collection*, through making previously hard to find information more accessible and understandable.

2.1 Aggregation & Data Mapping

Richards et al. (2025) provide a detailed description of the data collection, aggregation and hosting workflows. It begins with the underpinning ontology adapted from that used for ARIADNEplus (AO-Cat). ARIADNEplus in turn drew on CIDOC CRM, ensuring adherence to established best practice in the cultural heritage sector. AO-Cat is based around the three core attributes of What, When, Where, this was agreed by the Unpath’d team to be an appropriate starting point for this project. The updated version of this ontology was termed UO-Cat (Unpath’d Ontology).

Once the ontology had been agreed a process of data mapping was undertaken. This attempted to resolve differences between core datasets. Although controlled vocabularies have long been used by the national heritage agencies, for maritime craft were recorded in different ways, to differing levels of granularity. Rather than mapping between multiple vocabularies it was agreed to adopt the Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT), and map all data to that. While a clean solution to the problem, the granularity of Getty AAT did not match that given to maritime craft. While in the future this could be addressed through up-dates to the AAT, the ‘native subject’ field was used as a means of adding additional detail. Figure one shows this process in graphical form.

Within figure one a critical step of ‘enrichment’ is shown. This reflects the fact that while the above mapping of terms works in theory, it is only possible where there is sufficient match of detail in terms of fields and granularity of recording. In some instances, this was not the case. This is where the approaches developed by work package two helped to bridge the gap.

Figure 1 The workflow to upload data to the Graph DB triple store, including enrichment stages

3.1 The nature of the problem

For the mapping to the UO-CAT three facets were critical: Where, When and What. The different ways in which each of the NRHE had been created, and the way they had accumulated over time, meant that each dataset had very different qualities and affordances. This was true both within and between datasets. Thus, although controlled vocabularies, such as those given by the Forum on Information Standards in Heritage (FISH), had been utilised by national bodies, they may not have been used at the start of data collection (and thus not uniformly applied within datasets) or may not have been interpreted and used in the same ways. For much archaeological data specialist knowledge is required for interpretation, and this may lead to differing interpretations and encoding of that data.

For the mapping to UO-CAT a key challenge emerged around determination and mapping of ‘What’ in relation to the Welsh national record, Coflein. As noted above, Whilst the challenge was most apparent in this dataset, the underlying causes and implications could be seen in other datasets. Essentially, the problem was one of historical practice, of data being encoded relatively simply following the structure shown in table 1. This record contains a significant amount of important information, but much of it is concatenated within the ‘description’ field. Thus, while the resource type of ‘wreck’ was suitable for the needs of the record creator, it was not suitable for mapping to the UO-CAT in anything other than a very basic manner. More significant detail, however, is present within the description, the *Abbey* is a wooden sailing vessel, which sank in 1819, providing clearer data for both what and when. One of the key tasks was that of information extraction (IE), drawing critical data from dense text fields to enable integration of datasets.

Table 1 Excerpt of a shipwreck record from the Coflein database

NPRN	MMRW Name	Description	NMRW Heritage Resource type	NMRW Cultural Period	MMRW Evidence	OSGB Grid Ref.
272340	Abbey	“This record consists of a documentary reference to a shipping casualty which has been assigned to the maritime named location HOLYHEAD HARBOUR pending more information which may allow a more precise location for the loss to be assigned. Event and Historical Information: The ABBEY was a wooden sailing vessel. At time of loss on 30 August 1819, it was carrying a cargo of china clay from Charleston, Devon, to Liverpool under the command of master Cowling. The vessel is reported to have run onto the back slope of the pier at Holy-head and to have been bilged. Sources include: Larn and Larn Shipwreck Database 2002 Lloyds List, 21 September 1819, issue number 5423 Maritime Officer, RCAHMW, June 2008.”	WRECK	Post Medieval	Documents	SH2568882760

As discussed in Pink et al (in press), this challenge did not come as a surprise. Within the archaeological literature there is a clear thread for over thirty years marking out this problem. As Aberg and Leech (1992, 165) noted, the 1980s had been a period of rapid data capture, with the hope being that the 1990s could be one of data linkage and integration. The hope was clear that some of the challenges created by rapid data creation could be solved through technological advancement. Interesting Aberg and Leech (ibid, 167) argue that focus need not be on visualization (through emerging technologies like GIS), but increased accessibility and usability – it is very much a vision of a national collection of records. Sadly, as Richards (2006, 199) noted, things did not transpire as people had hoped. Instead, there was a surge of increased digitisation, but this increasingly digital record became no more coherent. As such, some of the challenges noted in the 1980s and 1990s remained in the datasets engaged with for this project. Fundamentally a number of these challenges relate to choices taken in data storage and data entry practices, pointing to the critical importance of these skills to bodies undertaking this task and, perhaps at key points in the past, an under-investment or under-valuing of them.

4.1 Artificial Intelligence and Record Enhancement

Pink et al. (in press) set out in detail the rationale and approach adopted in this project for record enhancement as well as giving an account of the broader literature on this topic. While still a relatively novel activity in archaeology, with a comparatively small number of publications (e.g Jeffrey et al. 2009, Richards et al 2015, Vlachidis and Tudhope 2016, Brandsen et al. 2022, Suissa et al 2022), techniques have been developed and deployed in other fields which are directly relevant and applicable to the challenges we face. At the start of

the Towards a National Collection programme a meeting of technical work packages across the five Discovery Projects was held. In this meeting it was agreed that a 'reduce, reuse, recycle' approach should be adopted when developing solutions to ensure maximum sustainability. Thus, rather than develop bespoke solutions, wherever possible establish routes should be tested and utilized. In addition, it was agreed that [FAIR](#) and [CARE](#) principles should be adhered to.

With this in mind a variety of different established approaches were tested in order to determine the most appropriate method for record enhancement for the datasets Unpath'd was engaging with. These included:

- supervised machine learning techniques,
- shot learning
- rule-based approaches.

It was recognized that this enrichment step was critical, as without it cross-search and analysis would be impossible due to dataset variability. To ensure we lived up to our FAIR commitments, all scripts developed were placed on the gitlab site. In order to assess which techniques performed best, accuracy, precision and recall values were generated. To do this a labelled dataset was prepared. This dataset was then split into 'train' and 'test' sets on a 70:30 ratio. Accuracy values were generated by comparing a models prediction for tests sets against the actual labels on the train set.

Precision and recall help to determine what sort of errors a model might be making. For every prediction the following determination is made:

- True Positives (TP),
- False Positives (FP),
- True Negatives (TN)
- False Negatives (FN).

Precision considers false positives and is calculated via: $TP/(TP + FP)$. Recall considers the impact of false negatives and is calculated via: $TP/(TP + FN)$. From these data an F1 value can be calculated, it is a blend of precision and recall as: $2 * (Precision * Recall)/(Precision + Recall)$.

4.2 Supervised Machine Learning

Two forms of supervised machine learning were trialled, Support Vector Machines and Random Forest:

Support Vector Machines

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) (Cortes and Vapnik 1995) are a class of supervised learning algorithms for classification and regression tasks. Supervised learning is a type of machine learning where a model is trained to make predictions based on labelled data. The model is presented with input data and the corresponding correct output, in this case the training dataset produced by Pink. The goal is to make accurate predictions on new, unseen data.

Random Forest

Random Forest is a supervised learning model (Breiman 2001). It is an ensemble learning method that combines multiple decision trees to create a "forest". Each tree is trained on a random subset of the data and a random subset of the features. To make a prediction using a random forest, the input data is passed through each decision tree in the forest. The output from each tree is combined to form a final prediction. In classification problems, the most common class predicted by the trees is selected as the final prediction.

Random Forest was implemented with TF-IDF. Use of TF-IDF here helped to identify the important terms within the fields in each record and facilitate classification. A separate model was implemented with Global Vectors for Word Representation (GloVe) (Pennington et al., 2014). GloVe creates a matrix based on the words that appear within in the context of a term. This matrix captures the meaning of the term and its relationships with other words in the vocabulary. GloVe was used with Random Forest for terms in the FISH thesaurus that did not have training data in the Coflein dataset.

4.3 Zero-Shot Learning

Zero Shot Learning (ZSL) utilizes an AI to learn, recognize and categorize new, unseen classes based on their understanding of relationships between known classes. Instead of explicit training, models utilize semantic associations between tokens (word- parts) to make predictions for novel instances. This enables systems to bridge the gap between familiar and unfamiliar concepts, expanding their capabilities.

Within Unpath'd Waters, the ZSL approach was be split into two kinds:

- records where the craft type is present in the rich text description
- records where type could be summarised from the description using domain expertise.

Where no ship type was present the record was passed to the ZSL algorithms (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 The complete ZSL Loop including a Cleaning Phase and the rule-based split to process individual records

A series of rules were created to be used with the ZSL based on the process Pink would take as a domain specialist to identify a vessel from these records. These are summarised in table 2:

Table 2 Rules applied as part of the Zero-Shot Learning approach

Rule	Description	Output
Rule 1	Matches all ship-type labels present in the text and returns a list. If only one label is present this is marked as a strong match. If more than one label is present it is sent through to the ZSL algorithms.	Ordered list of ship type labels present in text.
Rule 2	If similarity scores identify more than one label in an entry and a single preference cannot be identified preference is given to the label that occurs first in the sentence.	Ordered list of labels based on similarity and word location
Rule 3	Builds upon rule one. This tags labels returned by Rule One as nouns, spacy's pre-implemented library is used for parts of speech tagging.	Ordered list of labels based on use of ship type name as noun (avoids erroneous tags from verbs that match ship types such as: sailing, fishing and so on)

The similarity scores referenced by Rule 2 are included as table 3. Two ZSL implementations have been used. The first is trained on the Sentence Transformers repository (Reimers and Gurevych, 2019) and maps the text to a 384 dimensional dense vector space and finds the cosine similarity between each label and the text independently. The final prediction is the label that has highest similarity score. The second is trained on the MultiNLI dataset (Williams et al., 2017). This method deploys softmax classifier and distributes probabilities over all the labels. The label with highest probability values is returned.

2 Table 3 Similarity Scores for Sentence BERT ZSL and Facebook

Label	Sentence BERT ZSL	Facebook BART MNLI
tanker	0.29562	0.00527
trawler	0.24494	0.0034
schooner	0.23405	0.00472
submarine	0.23026	0.00338
barque	0.20950	0.00446
dredger	0.20717	0.0037
naval	0.20137	0.03228
barge	0.20076	0.00321
tug	0.19190	0.00439
liner	0.17651	0.00649
sloop	0.14961	0.00644
brig	0.14320	0.00232
yacht	0.13979	0.39251

ketch	0.11566	0.00417
lighter	0.11265	0.02292
craft	0.10871	0.28454
wherry	0.10382	0.01546
yawl	0.10137	0.01307
lugger	0.09451	0.0063
drifter	0.08355	0.01842
cargo	0.05608	0.0112
fishing	0.05578	0.00352
launch	0.054143	0.01809
smack	-0.003999	0.02922
transport	-0.00848	0.03024
patrol	-0.018542	0.00987
customs	-0.03886	0.02121
indiaman	-0.056150	0.00285
escort	None	0.01245
passenger	None	0.548

4.4 BERT, simpletransformers and Few Shot Learning

BERT or Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (Devlin et al., 2018) was the main model adopted by the Unpath'd team. This was the same choice made for AGNES (Brandsen et al., 2022) when undertaking a similar task. We used BERT-base-cased with the simpletransformers (Rajapakse, 2021) library's ClassificationModel class to define and train the model. These are used for sentence/text-level classification (multiclass text classification).

Few Shot Learning (FSL) enables a model to learn and make predictions from a small number of examples. It is particularly useful in situations where data is limited or expensive to obtain, such as that often seen in heritage datasets. One popular approach to FSL is to use a pre-trained model, fine-tuned on a small number of labelled examples from the new task. This was the method adopted here.

4.5 Human-in-the-Loop

'Human-in-the-loop' (HiL) refers to the involvement of a specialist in an AI-system. As shown in figure three this sees a domain expert reviewing and guiding the output of AI algorithms, correcting errors and providing insights. This feedback loop helps to refine the algorithm and enhance their performance. In this case an FSL model was deployed and Pink worked to generate the labelled dataset and correcting the predictions from the model.

Figure 3 Schema showing the Human in the Loop procedure adopted for Unpath'd Waters

4.6 Results

Of all the methods trialled FSL with HiL was the most successful and thus the one chosen to complete enhancement tasks. The tables (tables 4, 5 and 6) below detail accuracy, precision, recall and F1 scores for the final model. The successful implementation based off this kind of training data demonstrates how powerful FSL can be when combined with human domain expertise in this context. The model's accuracy was not impacted by the number of labels it was tasked with, indicating the model is robust and promising. The model used for FSL classification was fine-tuned on 70% of the dataset before testing. Some ship types like 'Wherry' had only one entry in the entire RCAHMW dataset. The algorithm took just over one minute to train and each prediction took about 0.5 seconds. Precision and recall are shown in Table X, where ship types had too few entries it was not possible to report precision and recall.

Shot-Learners perform significantly better when they are fine-tuned, even though they are designed to generalise on unseen domains. The results also show only FSL could map synonymous words. In the craft list the word "barque" is the best example as it is synonymous for the word "bark". Both words refer to a sailing vessel with square-rigged fore- and mainmasts and a fore-and-aft rigged mizzenmast and both terms are present in Coflein. Even though Support Vector Machines used the same training data, that model was unable to predict it accurately.

3 *Table 4 FSL results from implementations of BERT using different numbers of data sample*

Data Type	Model	Epoch	Batch Size	Accuracy
Data with at least 4 samples each	BERT	45	4	83.85
Data with at least 2 samples each	BERT	45	3	75.59

4

5 *Table 5 ZSL Accuracy Results for Facebook BART-MNLI and Sentence-BERT Models*

Configuration	Facebook BART-MNLI Accuracy	Sentence-BERT Accuracy
Without Rules	0%	29.86
With Rules	81.42%	89.95

6

7 *Table 6 Precision, recall and F1 scores for a selection of Maritime Craft types from the FSL model*

Ship Type	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Barge	1	1	1.000
Barque	1	1	1.000
Brig	0.8	1	0.889
Cargo	1	1	1.000
Craft	1	0.667	0.800
Dredger	1	1	1.000
Drifter	1	1	1.000
Fishing Vessel	0.667	1	0.800
Indiaman	0	0	None
Ketch	1	1	1.000
Launch	None	None	None
Lighter	1	0.5	0.667
Liner	None	0	None
Lugger	1	1	1.000
Naval Vessel	1	0.4	0.571
Schooner	1	0.8	0.889
Sloop	1	1	1.000
Smack	1	1	1.000
Submarine	0.8	1	0.889
Tanker	1	1	1.000
Transport	0.125	1	0.222
Trawler	1	1	1.0

4.7 Outcomes and Impacts

The enhancement work undertaken for this project, in collaboration with all other work packages, has helped to deliver some significant outcomes and impacts. Specifically:

- 325,000 new entries were created
- 25,000 records were enriched
- 13 fields were added

This was all achieved at a fraction of the cost in terms of person hours that would have been required to deliver the same results without AI assistance. Critically, for the first time the vision for the future of national heritage records set out in 1992 by Aberg and Leach has finally been arrived at. For the national inventories, it is now possible, for the first time, to bring the national record together allowing us to understand aspects of the unified record that were previously impossible to explore, including:

- Which records relate to physical objects
- which to documentary evidence
- what their distribution in time and space is
- Analysis of period of construction of wrecks across UK waters
- Identification of craft type for both documentary and physical wreck remains

We can also calculate a (heavily caveated) minimum number of wrecking events for UK waters. The caveats relate to the fact that documentary records only begin in earnest in the 1780s, with a considerable amount of maritime activity occurring before this date. These records are also poorer for smaller coastal vessels.

There are further outcomes and impacts that speak more to our practices as data managers and curators that are no less significant and detailed at the end of this report.

5. Testing Artificial Intelligence on Messages in Bottles

5.1 Introduction

This section of the report sets out the work done on the 'Messages in a Bottle Dataset' (MiB) an informal name used for a collection of newspaper articles that relate to literal messages in bottles found on beaches and afloat in the 19th and 20th centuries. The data was compiled by Ed Cumming and is hosted on the [Nautical Archaeology Society website](#). In this section of the report the affordances of the dataset are established with reference to its potential user-base and applicability to the wider aims of Unpath'd Waters, and the way it has been used as part of the Discovery Project.

The enhancement work done indicated the main userbase for this record is primarily those interested in narrative, or search for specific stories relating to individual people. The use of this dataset for any investigation should be enabled with significant caveats on its reliability, and lack of detail. The stories it contains, even the outright falsehoods, are uniquely engaging and can be used to establish a range of different narratives that would tie into areas of significant public interest. These are most notably the process of shipwreck, maritime crime, and stories of the sea and seafaring in the 19th and 20th centuries.

Following this introduction the methods used to approach the dataset will be set out. These cover the process of turning the Messages in Bottles record from a static PDF with limited functionality to a .csv file that is both machine readable and able to interact with other elements of Unpath'd Waters, most notably being ingested into the Unpath'd data viewer/ portal. The method for extracting Named Entities and Enriching key fields is also covered with reference to off-the-shelf models and tools. This is explored in relation to the projects values and the aim of minimising the use of 'bespoke' computational models.

The results demonstrate the effectiveness of creating a .csv dataset, review the number and type of entities that could be extracted, and essentially review the hard limits of what this process can achieve. This is an ideal dataset for the latter purpose as it contains what appear to be rich accounts of shipwreck events, however these accounts are demonstrably thin and lack the key information required to enable linkage to other shipwreck or ship-related datasets. This is then expanded on in a discussion that returns to the nature and origin of the Messages in Bottles. In this discussion the overall use of the dataset as a source of powerful and evocative narrative is a key theme. However, this is severely undermined by the presence of hoax, and fabricated records, and this is directly discussed in some of the original entries. All these aspects have a major impact on the linkage potential of this dataset and reinforces the essential inclusion of domain experts in the use of any maritime record.

The overall outcome from this work is the contribution of an engaging, partly fictitious, collection of records. It is a good example of a potential resource sink, with flaws and thin records initially masked by the evocative nature of the stories themselves. However, it makes a meaningful contribution to the work of Unpath'd Waters through the demonstration of Named Entity Recognition (NER), and the role of domain experts.

5.3 Methods

PDF to CSV

The data was initially provided as a PDF file with complex structure and formatting, including non-standard fonts (Figure 4). This is unsurprising for datasets of this kind, produced because of an individual undertaking a discrete piece of work. In the case of the MiB the records have been assembled as part of a Nautical Archaeology Society certificate.

1833

Dublin Evening Mail, [6/12/1833]: Loss at Sea – The **Mary Anne** from New York - The following was contained in a bottle, picked up a few days since on the shore, a few miles below Plymouth, by Mr. Curtis, of Falmouth:

"MARY ANNE (for the South Seas), Captain Westley, from New York, destroyed by fire at midnight, through the captain's cruel and drunken conduct, who was killed in the fire, 50 or 60 leagues from St. Jago. Some burnt, with the first officer, Mr. Wilson, who got u clear of the ship before she blew up. Our boats are so full we never can reach St. Jago. Pray let this be known, and mercy upon us in this boat – Miss Andrews, two children, Miss Manson, Miss Peot, Miss Doane, and Miss Watson, of the U.S.; nine seaman, and Mr. Wilson, late first officer; eight hundred ton".

Figure 4 Extract from the Messages in a Bottle pdf

The PDF was converted to CSV (comma delimited) file format. This conversion makes the dataset machine readable and therefore able to be processed by a suite of python-coded tools. The conversion was performed by splitting the data at key points in its structure. This was done by manually reading the text and identifying key points in the text that could be used to identify each field (as shown in Figure 5). This began as a relatively straightforward process. However, the text was not reliably readable by the programme created to convert the text. This challenge resulted in a messy output file that had to be manually checked and cleaned to ensure fields were split out correctly.

```
[ ] pages = [pdf.pages[i].extract_text() for i in range(len(pdf.pages))]  
  
#combine all the pages then apply regex because of entries like 1894 spread over 2 pages  
fullText = str()  
for page in pages:  
    fullText += page  
  
#extract years  
years = re.findall("\n\s*(\d{4})\s*\n", fullText)  
print(years)  
  
['1828', '1833', '1837', '1838', '1839', '1840', '1841', '1842', '1843', '1845', '1846', '1847', '1848', '1849', '1850', '1852', '1853', '1855', '1857', '1858', '1859', '1860', '1861', '1862', '1863']  
  
[ ] #find all the years first with corresponding descriptions and create a dataframe  
data = []  
years = re.findall("\n\s*(\d{4})\s*\n", fullText)  
for i in range(0, len(years)):  
    if i != (len(years) - 1):  
        sent = re.findall(years[i] + "\s*\n([\Ww]+)" + years[i+1], fullText)[0]  
    else:  
        sent = re.findall(years[i] + "\s*\n([\Ww]+)", fullText)[0]  
  
#clean data  
sent = sent.replace('&amp;', ' and ')  
sent = sent.replace('br', '')  
  
#add to dataframe  
data.append({'Year': years[i], 'Description': "\n"+sent.strip()})  
  
[ ] # Convert data to a Pandas dataframe  
df = pd.DataFrame(data)  
print(df.head())
```

Figure 5 Messages in a bottle CSV conversion process

Enrichment and Extraction

Once the dataset had been converted to a CSV file it was possible to further divide the dataset into key fields. The main aim of this approach was to establish three pillars of information: 'What', 'When', and 'Where' in the form of Name of Vessel, Date of Event, and Location or Co-ordinate of shipwreck event. This was expanded to include 'People' as these are another entity off-the-shelf tools could be used to identify. The aim with people was to divide between key groups such as 'Master', 'Owner', 'Crew' and others associated as MiB often named family members or onshore individuals to refer information of the wrecking on to. Once NER had been run it was then necessary to manually check the dataset and perform further correction. There is sometimes a degree of synonymy between ship names and the names of people. It was also often impossible to reliably distinguish between the roles of different people named in the record as this was not reliably stated in every account. All of this led to a manual checking of the dataset which became a fully manual extraction at times. When checking crossed the line into fully extracting data the process was truncated to produce a dataset with the minimum three 'What', 'Where', 'When' fields.

Information extraction was performed on the dataset using 'Flair'. This is an open-sourced Natural Language Processing framework by Zalando Research (see Akbik et al. 2019). Specific entities were extracted for columns headed Person (PER), Location (LOC), Organisation (ORG). This satisfies the initial search for 'What' and 'Who'. Ship names are more difficult as they are not restricted to nouns, shipowners using a variety of parts of speech as names for ships. Therefore a 'Miscellaneous' column was established that could capture ship names, this also captured other entities such as 'Lloyd's List' which was not returned as an organisation by the off-the-shelf Flair model. 'When' is extracted using the original dataset's dating information where each record is given a year and these are appended as their own column for each record. Finally, 'where' is established by extracting co-ordinates (where they are given) and Place Names (where they are given). The spatial data is imperfect as records often reference home ports, places bottles are found, or the location of onshore family/owners. This makes the identification of place more complex. During location tagging all entities that are tagged as 'location' by Flair are run through a second stage of process where the preceding word is checked to be 'to', 'from', or 'off' as this gives a greater level of control over location data with 'off' more likely to indicate a vessel was 'lost off [LOCATION]'.

Off the Shelf Tools

In all these stages the processing of the MiB was done with off-the-shelf tools and pre-trained Named Entity Recognition models. The benefits of this were an overall reduction in processing time, as models did not need to be trained to identify and extract different entities, thereby reducing both computing time, energy use, and human hours building the models. The main drawback to this is a messy 'best fit' output that combined names, misidentified people and ships, and required a degree of post-processing by a human domain expert. However, it is unlikely that a bespoke model would have performed any better due to a lack of data that could be used for training as the entire dataset is only a few thousand entries. This is a key factor of the deployment of NER tools on heritage datasets. None of the large unwieldy datasets encountered in the process of Unpath'd Waters are truly the 'Big Data' that is best suited for NER or other Machine Learning (ML) systems. Instead, the datasets fall into a difficult middle ground, they are not overly large and therefore able to provide reliable training datasets for bespoke models but are also large enough that manual processing and cleaning is tedious, difficult, and requires a significant investment of human hours. This means they are best suited for pre-trained off-the-shelf tools that automate a significant part of the process, and the result can then be handed to domain specialists to be checked, corrected, and finalised. MiB is an excellent example of all these traits and the need to include domain experts at every stage of the process will be further highlighted in the discussion.

5.4 Results and discussion

Readable CSV

The process has produced a readable CSV file. This serves as a stepping off point for further investigation using a variety of ML tools and allows for extraction processes to be run on the descriptions for each entry. There are some errors where the process to produce the CSV did not perfectly split records at their start and end points. This appears to be an issue caused by records overlapping individual pages in the original PDF file leading to imperfect extraction to CSV. However, this is relatively minor and only affected a handful of records so could be corrected manually.

Extracting Information

During entity extraction a total of 5886 entities were identified. The spread of these is set out in Table 7.

Table 7 NER outcomes for the Messages in a Bottle dataset

Miscellaneous	Person	Location	Organisation	From	To	Off	Coordinates (Lat, and Lon)
1329	1067	2426	627	160	86	146	45

The organisation of data into a CSV with location data enables display in a variety of geographical information packages. An example output in google maps is given here (Figure 6). This also helps to highlight some issues around automatic extraction of location-based data, with locations used in very different ways across records.

Figure 6 Map showing locations of named within the dataset

Challenges and Opportunities

The MiB work serves as a clear case study that demonstrates the value of converting datasets from static resources (in this case a PDF) to more versatile formats like CSV. The underlying dataset has the potential to contribute narratives that speak to a distinctly human existence at sea and the process of loss, wrecking, and the end-of-life circumstances of a ship. This is also an excellent dataset to foreground discussions of unreliable

narrators/witnesses and wider themes of 19th century wrecking, and a maritime environment where alongside the better-understood world of ship operation, shipbuilding, and trade there exist hoax, and falsehood. Therefore, the MiB has the potential to inform on the wider maritime world by providing an example of this behaviour.

There are however significant issues to connecting this dataset to its full potential. One challenge is the character of the dataset itself. Some records have considerable detail and context which enables ML tools to identify different entities easily and provide information that can be used to extract meaningful information. Other records are much thinner and lack specifics. There is no way to resolve this using ML Extraction tools as these can only be used to draw out information that is already available in the MiB.

Another challenge lies in the fact that a number of the messages are proven hoax or fabrication – some indeed have contemporary annotations from newspaper editors stating so. It is therefore very hard to determine what proportion of the dataset relates authentic accounts of sinkings. These potential issues highlight the role of an expert. Records like these are made more effective through the curatorial input of specialists who have studied and understand the nature of shipwreck and loss recording in this period. Without this input the dataset risks being presented as a factual recounting of hundreds of ship losses with all the same potential to inform on real world events as other key, more strictly maintained, loss lists such as the Lloyd's List casualty returns.

The majority however are likely to be examples that are genuine, last-ditch, messages recounting the loss of a ship at a time when no ship to shore communication existed.

A further challenge is connecting the MiB record to other maritime records, archives, datasets, or collections. This is the single biggest issue to the MiB. A dataset with good linkage potential is that of the Lloyd's Register of Shipping (LRS), this contains a record of every ship surveyed for entry into their register (then used for purposes such as insuring cargo, establishing a ship's condition and character, and providing owners with a guide to the state of their vessel). However, it is very hard to say a ship in MiB is the same as any ship in LRS. To achieve this effectively requires matching more than just a name, as names for ships are not unique and there can be many ships with the same name afloat at any one time. Unfortunately, there are only a handful of fields that are comparable between shipping registers (of any origin, not just the LRS) and the MiB.

One good case study of successful linkage is worth presenting, however. On 20th July 1843 the paddle steamer Pegasus, en route from Leith to Hull, struck Goldstone Rock as she was passing between the Farne Islands and the mainland. At least 43 of the 57 people aboard perished. The sinking was recorded in the Standard newspaper on 24th July. In October 1843, the message in the bottle was picked up at Wabourne, on the Norfolk coast, some 220 miles southward. Published in the Hull Advertiser and Exchange Gazette on 27th October, it stated "*PEGASUS, God help us! She is sinking! The bottles empty, will swim, and we also into eternity! Farewell! Elton*"¹. The story of the Pegasus, told in marvellous detail by Jane Bowen², includes a reference to another MiB, not in the Unpath'd Waters dataset which read: "*Pegasus steamer, to Fern Islands, night of Wednesday, July 19th, 1843. In great distress; struck upon hidden rock. On board fifty-five persons, vessel must go down, and no Grace Darling.*" This bottle was found on the Dutch coast in early November. The aforementioned

1

<https://unpathd.ads.ac.uk/resource/feb1e982fd732ec412146715156c6b7b76812c92241a60f4c6d36010cd6f353f>

² <https://www.islandshirearchives.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/The-Pegasus-story.doc>

Elton, author of the MiB was a famous actor Edward William Elton³. The wreck site itself is recorded both on the NHMR for England and Canmore, although the site is not 100% certain⁴.

Where the objectives of Unpath'd Waters are concerned this dataset demonstrates the effectiveness of off-the-shelf NLP tools, in this case Flair. However, the results also demonstrate the continued role of expertise and human review in ensuring the outputs reflect the information contained in the dataset. It is possible to use this dataset to show what is possible, but it is far more useful to use this as a case study of the limits of these tools and the need for a better overall approach to the recording and structuring of data in all records. Such an approach would create opportunities to truly link datasets through fields that would make such linkage more certain and therefore any further work better able to take advantage of an expanded maritime story.

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Edward_William_Elton

⁴

<https://unpathd.ads.ac.uk/resource/feb1e982fd732ec412146715156c6b7b76812c92241a60f4c6d36010cd6f353f>

Dead Reckoning: Work Package two recommendations

“The term ‘dead reckoning’, so the Admiralty Navigation Manual (1938) says, is a corruption of the old ‘deduced reckoning’ or ‘position by account’” (Taylor, E.G.R. 1950, 280)

Position by account, or dead reckoning is a key form of traditional maritime navigation. It is a method for knowing where you are (and where you should go) based on a detailed knowledge of where you have been. This stands as an apt metaphor for the challenges and opportunities represented by the digital datasets gathered together for Unpath’d Waters, and particularly for any aspiration to unite these records and create further links from them. As Aberg and Leech (1992) pointed out, the ways in which the national records have been constructed can be seen as problematic from a data consistency and linking point of view. Key observations are as follows:

- Although each of the national datasets demonstrate elements of best practice, and tailoring of data storage and entry to meet domain specialist needs, critical problems remain with tracking of data origins, qualities and updates. In effect, a diachronic process of knowledge generation is being reduced to a synchronic record that does not capture critical change. This is essential if meaningful links are to be established and any confidence in the record generated. We cannot navigate with a record that does not track its shifting position through time.
- All entries are treated alike, even if we treat these entities differently within archaeological ontologies and epistemologies. The fact that physical objects and records are given equal weighting is positive in one sense since it does not give primacy to the physical, but this also creates challenges around what each data point represents.
- To help resolve this tension it is recommended that physical objects and documentary records be given different persistent identifiers (PIDs) this would allow for a vessel name to be allocated and reallocated across physical entities as information changes. As the work of McCartney (2022) has demonstrated, the attribution of a vessel id to a wreck is frequently problematic.
- The current state of the maritime National Monuments Record(s) is not something artificial intelligence alone can fix. Crucially there is no way to cross reference (link) any site with anything outside the MNMRs beyond a very limited number of well investigated sites due to the way data is structured. The Welsh, Scottish and UKHO records take steps internally to address this through providing a ‘references’ and links field.
- Without the use of PIDs, linking of datasets remains highly challenging, even at the level of official reports.
- Default data entry practices can be problematic. It became apparent that within national records a ‘default’ position was taken on what data should be entered for particular fields if the specialist was unsure. The best example of this relates to period. Here for some national records ‘modern’ is the default entry if a specific date is not known, in others it is ‘post-medieval’. While this is understandable based on reasonable probability, it is highly problematic from an analytical point of view. If the Unpath’d Water’s portal is queried ‘schooners’ can be identified at the end of the Medieval period. This would be a phenomenal result if it were an accurate representation of knowledge, but is simply an outcome of default labelling (post medieval). Where something is not known it should be labelled as such.

- Challenges with maritime space persist. Each national agency has addressed the difficulty of precision and accuracy in determining wreck location differently, yet each provides coordinates (and some estimates of accuracy) for those points. Again, a specificity is offered at times beyond that demonstrated by the data. This can lead to easy misinterpretation by non-specialists.
- All of the above matters, as critical aspects of data quality are not immediately apparent from the datasets themselves. As more researchers utilise AI methods to draw on these large national datasets to carry out inquiry into the past, or shape the placement of future national infrastructure, the precision and accuracy of the record matters.
- The record for England currently only extends to the 12- nautical mile limit, and is thus not capturing data from offshore development, and with it the results of intensive and extensive offshore survey.

Dead reckoning, knowing where we are and where we should go is thus currently not possible without considerable work. That work cannot easily be completed by AI tools, or rather, needs to be split into a series of subset activities; to trace and map data origins, to consider data variability and veracity, as well as providing means to cope with the qualitative differences of data types held in the record. Critically, we have known of these problems since we first started adding data to digital systems. What this research has shown is that we can no longer put off addressing them as the potential for compound errors creeping in is considerable. These are records of national significance that need to be treated and valued as such, but clearly have not been valued or prioritised in this way in the past.

Unpath'd waters has shown that these issues are tractable and that the gains to be had are significant. More importantly they are also required if we are to make our shared cultural heritage accessible and manageable.

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